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Research Article

**INVESTIGATION OF WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY
OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF SARCOSTEMMA ACIDUM
LEAVES OINTMENT IN WISTAR ALBINO RATS****Arun Patil¹, Mallikarjun Patil², Sidhramappa chickpete³, Mohd Rafiq⁴ and
Satish Kalshetty⁵**¹Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy – Karnataka college of pharmacy.²Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy – Karnataka college of pharmacy.³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics – Karnataka college of pharmacy.⁴Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy – MAM College of pharmacy⁵Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology – MAM college of pharmacy.**Abstract:**

Aim. The present study was aimed at investigating the wound healing effect of aqueous extract of sarcostemma acidium leaves (AESAs) using excision wound model.

Methods. Wistar albino rats were divided into five groups each consisting of six animals; group I (left untreated) considered as control, group II (ointment base treated) considered as negative control, group III treated with 5% (w/w) povidone iodine ointment, which served as standard, group IV treated with AESA 2% (w/w) ointment, and group V treated with AESA 5% (w/w) ointment were considered as test groups. All the treatments were given once daily. The wound healing effect was assessed by percentage wound contraction, epithelialization period, and histoarchitecture studies in excision wound model.

Result. Different concentration of AESA (2% and 5% w/w) ointment promoted wound healing activity significantly in excision wound model. The high rate of wound contraction ($P < 0.001$), decrease in the period for epithelialization ($P < 0.01$), was observed in animal treated with AESA ointments when compared to the control and negative control group of animals.

Conclusions. aqueous extract of sarcostemma acidium (AESAs) leaves possesses a concentration dependent wound healing effect.

Keywords: Sarcostemma acidium, Wound healing, Aqueous extract

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INTRODUCTION:

A wound is defined as damage or disruption to the normal anatomical structure and function.¹ This can range from a simple break in the epithelial integrity of the skin or it can be deeper, extending into subcutaneous tissue with damage to other structures such as tendons, muscles, vessels, nerves, parenchymal organs and even bone.² Wounds can arise from pathological processes that begin externally or internally within the involved organ. They can have an accidental or intentional aetiology or they can be the result of a disease process. Wounding, irrespective of the cause and whatever the form, damages the tissue and disrupts the local environment within it. A physiological response to the noxious factor results in bleeding, vessel contraction with coagulation, activation of complement and an inflammatory response.^{3,4} Normal wound healing is a dynamic and complex process involving a series of coordinated events, including bleeding, coagulation, initiation of an acute inflammatory response to the initial injury, regeneration, migration and proliferation of connective tissue and parenchyma cells, as well as synthesis of extracellular matrix proteins, remodeling of new parenchyma and connective tissue and collagen deposition.^{5,6}

Sarcostemma acidum Roxb. Voigt is a xerophytic plant of the family Asclepiadaceae. Plant is locally known as Khair, Khimp, Khurasni tanto, Art thor, Soma and Somavalli. In English -Moon plant and moon creeper and in Hindi - Somlata.⁷ It is a traditional medicinal plant categorized as a member of soma plants used to prepare Somras. It is much branched, leafless, straggling shrub (Figure 1), climbing on *Euphorbia caducifolia* Haines on China hills. The plant found in India, Pakistan, and Europe.⁸ In India, it is mainly found in Bihar, West Bengal and many places of South India in dry rocky places at an altitude of 1350m⁹. It was also distributed widely over tropical and subtropical areas of Africa, America and Asia.¹⁰ Plants having long history in traditional health care application represent an understandable choice for scientifically investigation. It is fascinating to determine whether the traditional uses are supported by actual biological effects or merely based on folklore. Present study was designed to evaluate the wound healing potential of *Sarcostemma acidum* using excision wound model in Wistar albino rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection of Plant Material: Fresh whole plant material of *sarcostemma acidum* was collected from the local fields of Bidar. The plant specimen was

identified and authenticated by Prof. Dr. Srinath rao, Department of Botany, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga. A voucher specimen is preserved in the herbarium of Department of Botany (Voucher No.9108), Gulbarga University Gulbarga.

Extraction of Plant Material:¹¹⁻¹²

Preparation of Aqueous Extract

1. About 500gms of dried marc was taken in a 1000 ml of beaker and macerated with 500ml of distilled water to which 5ml of chloroform was added as a preservative and kept it for seven days with occasional shaking daily in a closed vessel.

2. The supernatant was decanted and the marc was pressed then the pooled extract was concentrated on water bath at 50°C to get a dry solid mass. The percentage yield was calculated and tabulated.

Experimental Animals:¹³

Albino Wistar rats of either sex weighing 100-150 gm were used for the study in excision wound model. Animal house was well maintained under hygienic conditions. The animals were housed in standard environmental conditions of temperature (31 ±1°C), humidity (60± 0.2%) and a 12 h light and 12 h dark cycle. They were provided with rodent diet and tap water ad libitum. Cleaning and sanitation work were done on alternate days. Paddy husk was provided as bedding materials, which was changed every day. The cages were maintained clean and all experiments were conducted according to the guideline's laboratory animal care.

Wound Healing activity:

Evaluation Parameters:

Measurement of Wound Contraction and Epithelialization Period.

In the excision wound model, wound area was measured by tracing the wound with the help of transparent sheet using milli meter-based graph paper on days 0, 4, 8, 12, and 16 for all groups. Wound contraction was measured every 4th day until complete wound healing and represented as percentage of healing wound area¹⁴. Percentage of wound contraction was calculated taking the initial size of the wound as 100% using the following formula: % wound contraction = (Initial wound area – Specific day wound area) / Initial wound area × 100. (1) Epithelialization period was calculated as the number of days required for falling off the dead tissue remnants of the wound without any residual raw wound¹⁵⁻¹⁶.

Effect of Aqueous extract of *sarcostemma acidium* on excision wound.

Treatment groups	Percentage wound contraction on				Epithelization Period (days)
	4th day	8th day	12th day	16th day	
Simple ointment base (B.P) (Control)	15.47 ±0.31	27.32±1.31	41.08±1.18	47.74±0.70	28.50±0.69
Providone iodine (Reference standard)	33.06±1.61	55.70±1.93	84.38±0.75	95.82±0.27	16.72±0.26
Test formulation (Aqueous Extract)	25.78±2.73	48.56±2.20	82.94±1.89	(100)	19.36±0.15

Values are mean ± S.E.M of 6 animals in each group. Numbers in parenthesis indicates percentage of wound contraction. ** p< 0.001 vs respective control by students 't' test.

CONCLUSION:

From the above mentioned studies it can be concluded that, The wound healing activity of aqueous extract of *sarcostemma acidium* was studied by using excision wound model and the extract showed significant wound healing activity

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